

Kinetics of the Oxidation of Pinacol by Acid Permanganate

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The main product of the oxidation of pinacol by acid permanganate is acetone. The reaction is of first order with respect to each of the oxidant and hydrogen ion. The order with respect to pinacol is one and two at high and low pyrophosphate concentration respectively. The rate increases by addition of manganese (II). The thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated. Mn (III) is possibly the active oxidising species and formation of reversible complex between pinacol and Mn (III) which decomposes to give a free radical is in accord with the observed data.

Oxidation of pinacol by manganic pyrophosphate has been studied by Drummond and Waters¹. However, there seems to be no report on the oxidation of pinacol by acid permanganate.

EXPERIMENTAL

Pinacol (B.D.H.) was used after distillation. Perchloric acid (Riedal) was used as a source of hydrogen ion. All other chemicals used were of A.R. quality.

Reactions were carried out in glass stoppered flasks at a constant temperature ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). Throughout the investigation the concentration of pinacol was kept in excess to that of permanganate. Aliquots, withdrawn at known intervals of time, were added to a slight excess of acidified ferrous ammonium sulphate solution and excess of ferrous ions left was estimated by titration with standardised permanganate solution.

RESULTS

Induced reduction of mercuric chloride: Acid permanganate oxidation of pinacol induces reduction of mercuric chloride. This indicates the formation of a reducing intermediate, i.e., a free radical¹.

Product Study: Oxidation of pinacol by acid permanganate gives acetone as the main product of oxidation. The amount of acetone formed was estimated gravimetrically as its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone.² The recovery of acetone is about 90% based on the following equation. No other product was detected.

Rate Laws: The rate of oxidation of pinacol by acid permanganate is very fast and to make the rate measureable, it was found necessary to add a suitable amount of

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1. A. Y. Drummond and W. A. Waters, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3119.
2. J. Mitchell, Jr., *Organic Analysis*, Vol. I, Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York (1953), 279.

pyrophosphate. When pinacol is in excess the rate at which permanganate disappears followed first order rate law (Table 1).

TABLE 1

A typical kinetic run

[Pinacol] = $4.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[H^+] = 0.92 M$, $[Na_4Py] = 3.75 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[KMnO_4] = 8.0 \times 10^{-4} M$,
Temp. 35°

Time in min.	0	2	10	17	20	24	30	37
($a-x$) ml. of KMnO ₄ soln.	5.6	5.4	4.7	4.1	3.9	3.6	3.2	2.8
$10^3 k_1$ (min ⁻¹)	—	18.2	17.5	18.3	18.3	18.4	19.1	18.7
		$10^3 k_1$ (min ⁻¹) = 18.3 ± 0.1						

In all cases the values of the first order rate constant were obtained graphically for first 30–40% of the reaction.

The order of reaction with respect to pinacol depends upon the ratio of pyrophosphate to pinacol. When the pyrophosphate to pinacol ratio is large, the order with respect to pinacol is one; but when this ratio is small the order with respect to pinacol is two (Table 2).

TABLE 2

Variation of rate with concentration of pinacol

(a) High pyrophosphate concentration

$[Na_4Py] 3.33 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[H^+] 1.0 M$, $[KMnO_4] 4.0 \times 10^{-2} M$. Temp. 40°.

[Pinacol] $\times 10^3$ mole l ⁻¹	4.0	6.0	8.0	10.0	12.0	16.0
$10^3 k_1$ (min ⁻¹)	4.20	6.50	9.21	11.0	13.8	19.0
$k_1/[Pinacol]$	1.05	1.08	1.15	1.10	1.15	1.18

(b) Low pyrophosphate concentration

$[Na_4Py] 2.5 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[H^+] 0.92 M$, $[KMnO_4] 8.0 \times 10^{-4} M$. Temp. 35°

[Pinacol] $\times 10^2$ mole l ⁻¹	2.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	6.0	8.0
$10^3 k_1$ (min ⁻¹)	6.13	14.0	24.2	40.0	64.0	103.0
$k_1/[Pinacol]^2$	15.3	15.5	15.1	16.0	17.7	16.0

Under the conditions of the constant ionic strength the rate varies linearly with the concentration of hydrogen ions (Table 3). The concentration of hydrogen ions were calculated after taking the buffering action of pyrophosphate ion into consideration.

TABLE 3

Variation of rate with concentration of hydrogen ion

[Pinacol] $4.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[Na_4Py] 3.75 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[KMnO_4] 8.0 \times 10^{-4} M$. Temp. 35°

$[H^+] M$	0.4	0.6	0.8	1.0	1.2	1.6
$10^3 k_1$ (min ⁻¹)	13.8	17.5	23.0	28.6	34.5	40.1
$10^3 k_1/[H^+]$	3.45	2.91	2.87	2.86	2.87	2.87

Effect of Mn(II) : Addition of Mn(II) ion increases the rate of oxidation but the rate soon reaches a maximum limiting value (Table 4).

TABLE 4

Effect of manganese (II)[Pinacol] $4.9 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[H^+]$ $0.92 M$, $[Na_4Py]$ $5.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ [KMnO₄] $8.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[MnSO_4 + ZnSO_4]$ $3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, Temp. 35°

$[Mn^{+2}] \times 10^4$ mole l^{-1}	0.0	4.0	12.0	20.0	30.0
$10^2 k_1$ (min ⁻¹)	2.42	3.68	4.61	4.61	4.61

TABLE 5

Effect of temperature[KMnO₄] $8.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ $[Na_4Py]$ $3.75 \times 10^{-2} M$

Temp. °C	30	35	40	45	ΔH^*	ΔS^*
$10^3 k$ ($l^3 \cdot mole^{-3} sec^{-1}$)	11.3	20.8	36.5	60.6	21.0 ± 1 kcal mole ⁻¹	7 ± 0.3 e.u.

Effect of Temperature : The data on the effect of temperature on the rate of oxidation are summarised in Table 5. It is found that a plot of $\log k$ against inverse of temperature gives a straight line. Arrhenius equation is, therefore, valid for this reaction. The specific rate constant, k , was calculated by the relation :

$$k = \frac{k_1(\text{min}^{-1})}{60[\text{Pinacol}]^2[H^+]}$$

The thermodynamic parameters were calculated in the usual manner.

DISCUSSION

The effect of manganese (II) on the rate of oxidation indicates that Mn(III) is the active oxidising species. This is supported by the ability of pyrophosphate ion to control the reaction. In presence of excess of sodium pyrophosphate Mn(III) probably exists as manganic pyrophosphate.

The increase in the rate of oxidation with increase in the hydrogen ion concentration may be attributed to the effect of acidity on the redox potential of Mn(III)/Mn(II) system.³

The second order dependence on pinacol may well be due to replacement of two pyrophosphate ions from Mn(III) pyrophosphate by pinacol at one pyrophosphate concentration, to form a complex which decomposes in the rate determining step. At high pyrophosphate concentration obviously pinacol is able to replace only one pyrophosphate ion.

3. H. Land and W. A. Waters, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2129.

The energy of activation, the entropy of activation and the product analysis indicate that the oxidation of pinacol involves a C-C bond fission as in the case of other glycols by manganic pyrophosphate⁴. In fact Duke⁵ has suggested that reactions involving C-C bond fission via complex formation has energy of activation of the order of 20-25 kcal mole⁻¹. Bakore and Narayan⁶ have also postulated that reactions involving C-C bond fission have small values of the entropy of activation.

Thus it appears that Drummond-Waters scheme¹, i.e., the formation of a reversible cyclic complex between pinacol and manganese (III) pyrophosphate and its slow decomposition to give a free radical satisfactorily account for the observed kinetics of the reaction. The initial formation of Mn(II) may be accounted by the following dynamic equilibrium⁷.

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4. P. Levesly, W. A. Waters and A. N. Wright, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 840.
5. F. R. Duke, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 2885, 3054.
6. G. V. Bakore and S. Narayan, *Z. Physik. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1964, **227**, 8.
7. R. W. Malcom and R. M. Noyes, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 2709.